

FROM AGROINDUSTRIES TO INTEGRATED BIOMASS LOGISTICS CENTRES. AGROINLOG PROJECT: SUMMARY OF FINAL RESULTS

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ABSTRACT: AGROinLOG project has tested the integrated biomass logistics centres (IBLC) concept in three real agro-industries in Europe. The relevance of the IBLC strategy relies on the fact that it allows agro-industries to create a new activity with lower investment, increasing incomes, stabilizing their annual activity (avoiding idle periods) and maintaining or creating new jobs. The demos' studies were performed in Spain at a fodder industry, in Greece at an olive oil industry, and in Sweden inside a cereal processing industry. AGROinLOG validated these demos' business models from a holistic perspective, also studying the replicability of the IBLC business model in other agro-industries from different sectors (vegetable oil extraction, olive oil chain, feed & fodder, wine, grain chain and sugar industry). Sectorial analysis was carried out as well, allowing the identification of opportunities among the targeted sector to replicate the IBLC concept, drawing barriers to overcome in each case. Thus, technical, economic and environmental feasibility of integrated biomass logistics centers (IBLCs) for food and non-food products have been assessed in detail.

Keywords: agroindustry, biobased economy, biomass, circular economy

1 INTRODUCTION

Many European agro-industries are characterized by the fact that capital goods and facilities cannot be used year-round due to the seasonal availability of their primary feedstocks. AGROinLOG project aims to improve the competitiveness of agro-industries through their transformation into Integrated Biomass Logistics Centres (IBLC). An IBLC is a business strategy that takes advantage of unexploited synergies in terms of facilities, equipment and staff capacities, to diversify regular activity both on the input (food, feed and biomass feedstock) and output side (food, feed, biocommodities & intermediate biobased feedstocks), thereby enhancing the strength of agro-industries and increasing the added value delivered by those companies. Becoming an IBLC thus increases the competitiveness of an agro-industry by for instance opening new markets, prolonging their operational periods and retaining employees in their idle periods.

Three different sectors and demos have been studied in AGROinLOG in three different European countries in

which these agricultural activities are of relevance, being the olive sector in Greece, feed & fodder sector in Spain and grain processing in Sweden.

The olive oil sector is one of the most important agricultural sectors in Greece as it contributes more than 0.4 % to the national GDP with a total annual sales of 832.7M€ [1]. Greece is the third olive oil country in terms of olive oil productivity worldwide with over 2,400 industries in the sector [2]. Many agricultural areas in Greece dedicate their crops to olive tree cultivations. The pruning of which produces a great amount of agricultural biomass (olive tree prunings) that remain untapped and mostly burned in open fires or scarcely mulched onto soil. This reality offers a great opportunity to existing agro-industries in the sector in exploiting such raw material and upgrading it into added value products. The development of new business activities in existing agro-industries enhance their competitiveness and revenues.

In the meantime, feed and fodder sector in Spain consists of mixes of different crops such as: barley, wheat and oats, whole crop silages, peas and broad beans, maize for forage, clover and alfalfa (lucerne), among others.

More specifically, in Spain, 85 % of the raw materials for dehydrated fodder industries corresponds to Lucerne, mainly destined to feedstuff. Currently, there are 70 fodder dehydrator industries and almost 1,500 feed industrial manufacturers in Spain. The total cultivated area in Spain of forage crops covered almost 1.1 million ha in 2014, presenting a feedstuff production of 23.3 million tonnes (2015) and a 1.61 million tonnes fodder production between 2016-2017. Particularly, the average value of the industrial production of compound feedstuff in Spain reached €6,820 million and €300 million in the case of fodder plants production.

As for the grain sector in Sweden, the total area of cereals was on average 1,011,307 ha between 2012-2016. This accounted for around 40 % of the total arable land in Sweden. The distribution between the different types of cereals was as following: 328,716 hectares of winter wheat, 83,468 hectares of spring wheat, 22,917 hectare of rye, 14,213 hectares of winter barley, 337,082 hectares of spring barley and 182,128 hectares of oats. Between 2012 and 2016, the total annual grain harvest was approximately 5.5 million tonnes. Sweden is self-sufficient in cereals and usually has a grain surplus that is exported mainly to other EU countries, but also to countries outside the EU. The cultivation of cereals generates around 3,080 annual work units (AWU) in Sweden (LRF, 2016). The milling and starch industry generate around 1,587 AWU in Sweden, the bakery industry 14,505 AWU and the malt brewing industry 2,060 AWU.

From an overall view, these sectors represent over 10% turnover of agro-food industries and 30% of those with inherent synergies to integrate food and non-food business taking advantage of their existing equipment, seasonality, and established food logistics. The synergies of applying IBLCs business in existing agro-industries can have a positive impact over 18 % in final product price, giving a clear competitive strength to a wide segment of agro-industries, which can exploit this privileged situation compared to a new biomass supply business built from scratch.

An IBLC refers to the start of new biomass activity involving different aspects, such as field harvesting, collection and procurement towards the agro-industry, transformation into a higher added value commodity (bales, pellets, woodchips, etc.) and marketing. This requires the development of a new non-food value chain that should be integrated with the pre-existing food chain. IBLCs by their conception, can substantially contribute to the European strategies.

Thus, IBLCs include a series of unique synergies for the development of new business on biomass and for the strengthening as agroindustries. However, there are three cornerstones for the synergy of food and non-food logistics in the agroindustry [9]:

- Seasonality of the works in some cases: the agro-industries could use their personnel and facilities during their idle period for extending the activity along the whole year by alternating the food and non-food production.
- Existing equipment and facilities: the company can take advantage of their existing equipment for handling and conditioning biomass (drying, pelletising, storing) during seasonal periods of low food activity.
- A developed contact network: agro-industries already have a network of suppliers and clients, and thus they can use them for obtaining biomass from their current

providers, and can find in their current suppliers and clients a niche of market for biomass derived products.

Therefore, this article presents the technical and economic feasibility of a new bio-based value chain concept assessed in different agro-industries and important factors to be carefully evaluated while an agro-industry of the sector decides to advance towards its transformation into an IBLC.

For this aim, a wrap-up of the most relevant contributions of AGROinLOG project will be presented, considering: (i) key aspects of sustainable Business Models for the Agroindustry; (ii) identification of potential bioproducts and bio-commodities for the grain, feed and fodder and olive sector agroindustries based on the demo cases; (iii) key factors related to logistics in IBLCs; (iv) most relevant features contributing to optimize the environmental, social and economic impact; (v) identification of European regions and agricultural sectors with high potential to replicate the IBLC concept and (vi) generic strategies for IBLC concept implementation in agro-industries.

2 OBJECTIVES

2.1 Main objectives of AGROinLOG

The project is built on the agro-industries in the fodder, olive oil production and cereal processing sectors that have define and optimize the IBLC concept and the assessment of the replication potential for different sectors.

Main challenges are based on being able to integrate logistics, harvesting and equipment in food and non-food applications, where the project is focused, ensuring marketability of the final bio-commodities.

AGROinLOG will apply a multi-actor approach to attain experiences and knowledge of the sectors and agro-industries, enhancing the accuracy of the business models and developing effective and friendly guidelines of best practices to replicate and spread IBLC concept in Europe.

This project will contribute towards employment stability – seasonality avoidance-, rural development and bio-economy goals.

AGROinLOG's ambition is to go beyond the demo sectors, providing Europe with the practical knowledge to foster that a large share of the potential sectors adopts potential synergies of the food and non-food activities.

2.2 Objectives of AGROinLOG in the olive oil sector (Greece)

The existing chain sought to create a highly integrated logistics centre to complement their activity with the production of solid biomass and the biochemical, expanding their business over unused resources and solving problems that these resources generate. The following opportunities within the AGROinLOG project were identified:

- Mainly use of olive tree pruning as a feedstock for the production of solid biofuels.
- Use of olive tree prunings for the production of bio commodities (e.g. particle boards) or extraction of useful chemicals from residual streams. In particular, olive leaves or pomace have high phenol content; extracted phenols would also be a useful chemical for applications in industrial sectors such as the pharmaceutical or cosmetics industry.

2.3 Objectives of AGROinLOG in the feed & fodder sector (Spain)

The new business line has been conceived to take advantage of the idle period of the equipment in the plant from December to March. During this time, new pellets for two different purposes will be produced: energy use and bio-composite materials. With AGROinLOG approach, the aim of the plant has been to increase its flexibility by enabling the production of new pellets from cereal straw, maize stalks during the current season of inactivity with a negligible investment. Furthermore, two other markets were tackled with these new products: thermoplastics reinforced with natural fibers, adsorbents for hydrocarbons spills, activated carbon, biocomposites and furfural and levulinic acid obtaining.

2.4 Objectives of AGROinLOG in the grain sector (Sweden)

The new business activity includes the use of straw as a new feedstock in the current process of producing bioethanol to achieve products of higher value from the whole straw value chain.

The existing bioethanol plant is depending on grain market prices. For this reason, during some periods, the plant operates in partial load or has to purchase other feedstocks like sugar that, as well as the grain, does compete with the food market. In order to avoid these problems and make the process economically more attractive, the farmers' cooperative Lantmännen aims to diversify the feedstock by using straw as a non-food source to obtain second generation bioethanol and biooil and biogas from the wastewater treatment.

2.5 Replication of the IBLC model in other agroindustries

Throughout the life of AGROinLOG, teams have sought to understand the views and needs of sector stakeholders so as the replication potential of IBLC model in other agro-industries. In this context, the replication potential was also studied in the following sectors: wine, feed and fodder, olive oil, grain and sugar.

3 METHODOLOGY

Two different methodologies will be reported in this work. Firstly, different considerations were taken into account in order to assess the technical and economic feasibility of the IBLC concept in the specific sectors studied in the three demo cases (Greece, Spain and Sweden), such as:

- Raw material availability
- Harvesting and supply chain
- Biomass storage
- Production process
- Definition of blends (when it applied)
- Product quality
- Market analysis
- Validation activities (when it applied)
- Cost structure and investment necessary in the new business model(s)
- Advantages/drawbacks of IBLC implementation

As for the study of the replication of the IBLC model in other sectors, a specific methodology was developed, consisting of 3 steps:

- 1 Preliminary identification of regions with high potential for IBLC development from the experience

gathered in the AGROinLOG project.

- 2 Interview with agro-industries and high-level contacts in the selected region on regional potential, barriers and incentives for IBLC implementation allowed to extract valuable information regarding these topics.
- 3 Workshops with regional stakeholders where the findings from the task were shared and feedback sought

4 MAIN RESULTS

4.1 Demo case in the Olive oil sector (Greece)

The demonstration of the olive sector was performed in Greece and was centered on NUTRIA S.A., as the agro-industry demo partner, with the collaboration of CERTH as the principal demo technical supporter. The following results are part of the public deliverable D4.8 'Success case of the integration of a logistics centre into an agro-industry of the olive oil sector' [3].

NUTRIA operates an olive oil mill and a larger oil refinery plant that produces standardized olive oil, pomace oil and seed oils. NUTRIA's facilities are located in Agios Konstantinos, Fthiotida, Central Greece and the implementation of the IBLC concept is based on the exploitation of an untapped local biomass resource, olive tree prunings (OTP), mainly as feedstock for energy production.

NUTRIA is located in the town of Agios Konstantinos, Fthiotida, where 1,100 ha of olive groves are located. The Agios Konstantinos olive groves are part of an extended zone of olive tree cultivation in the coastal part of Fthiotida, where more than 34,000 ha of olive groves are located.

During the AGROinLOG project, NUTRIA and CERTH and based on preliminary results achieved during the project lifetime, considered three different concepts for exploiting local OTP biomass. Each concept targets different types of end-users and requires different levels of investments:

- Concept A, OTP hog fuel sales: NUTRIA remains with the existing infrastructure and equipment (the one integrated harvester/ shredder and storage/handling facilities of NUTRIA) and becomes a logistics centre for harvesting, storing, handling and selling hog fuel derived from olive tree prunings. The hog fuel is produced for external consumers (e.g. biomass power plants, industrial biomass consumers). That would be mean around 2,500 tons of hog fuel harvested per year
- Concept B, OTP pellet plant: NUTRIA invests on an OTP pellet plant. The OTP pellets will be sold in the Greek market for solid biofuels.
- Concept C, OTP power plant: investment on a biomass power plant of 1 MWe that will be using exclusively the hog fuel of OTP. Electricity generated will be sold directly to the grid.

4.1.1 Raw material availability

Local olive tree varieties are mostly targeting edible olive production and are characterized by their high vigour, e.g. high biomass productivity from prunings. Local conditions in Agios Konstantinos have been assessed via questionnaires, while a GIS tool estimating the OTP availability, extended to the whole region, has been developed by CERTH.

Figure 1: GIS mapping tool developed by CERTH. Olive groves in Agios Konstantinos

Overall, it is estimated that OTP availability in a radius of 5 km from NUTRIA is 5,000 dry tons of OTP, which increases to 10,000 dry tons when the radius is extended to 10 km. Overall, all investment concepts can be implemented while keeping the sourcing radius short.

4.1.2 Harvesting and Supply Chain

Local conditions in Agios Konstantinos, specifically the distance between trees and the relatively flat fields, favor mechanized harvesting of OTP prunings. Within AGROinLOG, different harvesting options have been assessed by project partners CERTH and CREA; the integrated harvesting/shredding options using tilting bins for discharge of the material was ultimately selected as the most appropriate and mature option for harvesting OTP biomass in Agios Konstantinos.

During the project's duration, two large harvesting demonstrations were organized in 2018 and 2019. The main technical implement used for the demonstration was a Facma Comby TR200 harvester/shredder. The harvesting demonstration were implemented by the Agricultural Cooperative of Agios Konstantinos, under the supervision and support of project partners CERTH, INASO-PASEGES and NUTRIA. More details on the first harvesting campaign of 2018 can be found on the published work [4]. In brief, the harvested areas were 53.8 ha for 2018 and 27.2 ha for 2019, resulting in the collection of 174 and 78 dry tons of OTP hog fuel respectively. Improvements in harvesting performance was noted in the second year of the demonstration, due to the accumulated experience of the operators.

Through the detailed monitoring of harvesting and haulage operations recorded in the demonstration, it is estimated that a final productivity of 2.5 dry tons of OTP per hour can be achieved in commercial operation. The total cost of harvesting and transporting OTP in nearby storage area (5-10 km) is calculated as 33 €/wet ton, with a 27.5 % weight average moisture content. The harvesting cost is considered as being quite competitive, where it can further be compressed. Further details on the operational performance of the harvester can be found on the published paper [5].

OTP biomass is available only for a few months of the year. In Agios Konstantinos, the olive trees are generally pruned from February to March. Local farmers wish to be rid off the OTP biomass as soon as possible, and definitely before the summer months, since it is an obstacle to other agronomic operations as well as potential fire hazard. This means that the OTP harvesting season can extend from February to latest May, thus requiring long-term storage solutions for the yearly operation of an IBLC concept.

Within AGROinLOG, storage of OTP hog fuel piles during the summer till early autumn months was

evaluated. Two different options were assessed: uncovered storage and storage under a breathable fleece. The first option corresponds to zero additional costs, while the second is a low-cost alternative to roofed storage. The fleece-covered pile storage ultimately resulted in a net energy content gain of 12.1 %, while keeping dry matter losses at 1.1 % after six months of storage. The uncovered storage resulted in higher dry matter losses of 4.6 % and an energy loss of 5.1 %.

4.1.3 Production Process

For the case of NUTRIA, the production process is different depending on the concept.

Concept A (hog fuel sales) requires minimum to no additional processing, beyond loading of the product from the storage area to a truck for transport to a final consumer.

Concept B (pellet production) has been demonstrated within the AGROinLOG project in a commercial, modern pellet production facility in Greece, where a quantity of OTP hog fuel was transported and OTP pellets were produced. The heat consumptions required for the pelletization of the OTP amounted to 1044 kWh primary energy per dry ton of produced pellet. In overall, the heat consumptions required for the pelletization process amount to the 69 % of the total energy consumption of the whole value chain, from biomass harvesting to pellet production. Regarding the electricity demands required for the pelletization, that amounts to 295.5 kWh primary energy per dry ton of produced pellet or 20 % of the total consumption of the whole value chain. Finally, based on the feedback retrieved during the pellet production, the pelletization cost was estimated around to 80 € per ton of pellet produced.

Figure 2: OTP pellets

Concept C (power plant) has not been specifically demonstrated at industrial scale within the AGROinLOG project due to this approach was developed in the last months of the project. However, the concept is based on the operation of a gasification biomass power plant (with an installed capacity of 1 MWe) in Northern Greece. This plant applies biomass gasification, followed by combustion of the produced syngas in internal combustion engines.

4.1.4 Product Quality and Market Analysis

The current section contains information on the final properties of the new products of NUTRIA as an IBLC (OTP hog fuel and pellets). The Information on the final product quality and fuel properties derived from the demonstration activities (both harvesting and pelletization). Finally, the results of the validation activities of such products are presented, that shows the performance of the new products compared to other

competitive fuels of the market.

In brief, OTP fuels have a good energy content but differ from forest biomass in terms of higher ash content. Thus, this type of biomass requires boilers with higher requirements in the systems dedicated to withdraw ashes or to clean the flue gases. Even though OTP pellets could compete with well-established industrial fuels, in terms of combustion efficiency and emissions, their cost is considerably higher (150 €/t), making them an unattractive solution for substituting industrial fuels.

The use of OTP in the form of hog fuel seems to be a promising solution. It is a more competitive biofuel due to its reduced fuel cost (50 €/t). However, it faces several challenges as well, as its need of a suitable feeding system to burn such fuel. Furthermore, OTP hog fuel has significantly lower (energy) density compared to pellets, thus increasing the transportation costs. In this light, its targeted end users should be in close range from the IBLC.

For Concept C, the main advantage is that electricity sales from biomass are eligible for a feed-in premium in order for operators to reach a reference tariff for a period of 20 years through a contract with the grid operator. Hence, NUTRIA would not have to deal with variations in demand and can concentrate on securing biomass fuel supply for uninterrupted plant operation.

4.1.5 Cost Structure and Performance of New Business Model

In brief, for Concept A (hog fuel commercialization), NUTRIA will not perform any significant investment and could start its new IBLC activity with its current equipment and facilities. In this concept, no new investments are required. However, the new personnel required would be 5 seasonal employees in the harvesting (one harvester required), and transportation of hog fuel to NUTRIA and one part-time employee that would attract and interact with customers. The harvested OTP will be sold as hog fuel in few close-ranged industries or public buildings, with a selling price of around 50 €/tw.b. from the IBLC gate. The commercialization of 2,500 tons hog fuel will increase the annual turnover of NUTRIA by 125 k€.

For Concept B, NUTRIA will invest around 0.6 M€ for a pellet line of 1 t/h. Regarding the personnel that would be required in the concept of the pellet plant, three full time workers per shift and two shifts would be needed, thus 6 workers per day. A seventh specialised operator would be in charge of the maintenance and supervision for the two production shifts. Again, around 15 seasonal employees would be needed for the harvesting of prunings (three harvesters required). Another person will be needed for administration, logistics and sales activities. For the case where OTP pellets are produced, based on the results obtained so far, it has been estimated that these pellets could be sold in the Greek market at a price around 150 €/ tw.b. for the OTP-pellet. For an annual production of 5,000 t of OTP-pellets, NUTRIA will obtain around 0.75 M€ turnover per year in this new business.

For Concept C, NUTRIA will invest on a power plant (1 MWe). The investment cost would be around 4 M €. The additional personnel that will be needed, will be 9 permanent employees operating in the power plant and 15 seasonal employees in pruning harvesting and transportation (three harvesters required). For the case of the power plant, the annual revenue for NUTRIA will be

coming from selling electricity to the grid. By assuming a selling price of 185 €/ MWh, the turnover of NUTRIA would be increased by around 0.8 M€ annually.

IBLC implementation in the agro-industry

4.1.6 Other biocommodities from olive oil sector

Apart from the exploitation of olive prunings for energy purposes, the production of other biocommodities. In this light, AGROinLOG investigated the potential of producing three biocommodities: particleboards from olive prunings, polyphenols from olive oil sector residues and OTP pellets as animal bedding.

The obtained particleboards were produced by replacing common wood at 20 %, 40 %, 60 %, 80 % and 100 % rate. They were tested for their tensile strength, thickness swelling, modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity, moisture resistance and formaldehyde emission, in accordance with the current European standards, and compared with the same values of reference associated to particleboards produced from conventional wood material.

The evaluation of the results has led to the conclusion that it is possible to produce panels with a maximum substitution level of 40 % of the conventional wood with pruning material. The mechanical properties of the panels are reduced by increase of the substitution level. This may be attributed to the higher amount of bark compared to the conventional wood chips, which are produced from debarked wood logs. On the other hand, particle board properties such as the formaldehyde emissions of the boards (along with the thickness swelling) are reduced by increase of the substitution level, which makes the panels safer in terms of indoor pollution and human health and more consumer friendly and attractive.

Figure 3: Particleboards produced (UF resin) from reference wood (a), particle boards produced with 40% (b) and 100% (c) substitution from harvested with integrated mulcher/harvester prunings, 40% substitution with prunings with leaves, separated manually (d), and 40% substitution with firewood (thick olive prunings, e)

The cultivation and processing of the harvested olive fruits yields various by-products such as field residues (leaves, prunings) and mill residues (pomace, exhausted olive cake), that consist an interesting source of phenolics. The total polyphenols market was estimated in 2010 to about 2.2k t of polyphenols [6], whereas, it is calculated that Greece has an annual discharge of polyphenols of about 2.4k t polyphenols. However, the

options for integration of phenol extraction technology in the olive mill facilities needs further evaluation as the volume of the market for specific extracts is not yet known.

In the frameworks of AGROinLOG, extraction tests were performed on various olive mill waste residues with different solvents. Quantitative analysis showed OL (olive leaves) and TPOMW (two-phase olive mill waste) contained the highest content of phenols compared to the other samples (exhausted olive cake, OTP, bark etc.), with a content of phenolics of 15.7 and 12.4 g of phenols/dry kg solids of residue respectively. In addition, some of the phenolic components were identified in the extracted phenols such as oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol, 1,2 dimethoxy benzene, rutin and caffeic acid. By using different kind of solvent, not only the amount of phenolic compounds extracted was different but also the type of phenols extracted differed.

Finally, an interesting possibility that can “revive” the pellet concept is to sell OTP pellets as an animal bedding material. Indeed, pellets from forest wood or “alternative” biomass feedstocks suggested for animal bedding can be found in various countries and it seems that straw pellets available in Greece are mainly targeting this market segment. In this context, OTP pellet was used as a bedding in a bunny’s house. The pet owner highlighted her satisfaction for using the OTP pellets, commenting that they have better smell and their color is darker so the bunny’s house looks cleaner. In addition, the OTP pellets do not disintegrate into very fine dust when wet. Although extremely limited in scope, this activity indicated the potential of selling OTP pellets in the niche market of animal bedding. In fact, it seems that in this market, the OTP pellets may even be sold at a premium compared to wood pellets since their properties are better.

4.2 Demo case in the Feed and fodder sector (Spain)

The implementation of IBLC model in the fodder sector was studied through the collaboration during the project of Agroindustrial Pascual Sanz (APS). The following results are part of public deliverable D3.7 ‘Success case of an IBLC into an agroindustry of the animal feed sector’ [7].

Agro-industries in the fodder sector normally account with a dehydrated business line to produce high compression bales of lucerne for instance, and a pelletization line to produce pellets for the animal feed market. This activity is mainly taking place between the months from April to November, since the arrival of the loose raw material is what mainly defines the timeframe of the production. In the case of the pellet production this line operates the whole year according to customers’ needs and electrical tariffs, although the production capacity is reduced from December to March.

The development of energy blends pellets for energy market based on herbaceous materials and forestry woodchips was proposed. Additionally, outside this scope, other studies were performed in order to assess the possible use of pure herbaceous material to produce thermoplastic reinforced with natural fibres, activated carbon, adsorbent for hydrocarbons spills, bio-composites, and furfural and levulinic acid. The results obtained were very promising, although in the short-term the commercialization of this product for these purposes is difficult since the market is not yet well developed.

4.2.1 Selection of raw materials

The chemical composition of the biomass has a huge variability associated to the area where these crops are cultivated and to other parameters like the management of the crop or climate conditions. For this reason, and in order to optimize the percentage of wood needed, a traceability assessment of the wheat straw and corn stalk was carried out. To this aim APS’ main suppliers were identified, and the corresponding main storage areas studied and representative samples were taken from these different areas in order to analyse the quality of these raw materials (see Table I).

As a result of the traceability assessment carried out, two areas (E and F) were selected in which the material had better properties for energy uses than the others. In the case of maize stalk, the work carried out was not as intensive as with wheat straw due to rainfalls during the campaign of 2018, for this reason the study was limited to two areas in Zaragoza, picking up the material from the area B.

The influence of the material storage on the dry matter losses was also studied. It was observed that wheat straw increased 5 % its moisture content during the storage period (from 7 to 12 %-w/w) in contrast to corn stalk which decreased it 2 % (from 13 to 11 %-w/w). In the case of wheat straw, the dry matter losses were just 0.5 % but for the corn stalk is almost 4 %. In both cases, the conditions of the bales located on the top are strongly dependent on the rainfall. LHV presents some variability along the months but in both cases the values were quite constant. Ash content evolution showed behaviours not only related to loss of dry matter during the storage, which would have implied obtaining increasing ash content values in all the cases.

Table I: Results of the traceability assessment carried out for the wheat straw and maize stalk in 2018

Traceability assessment for the wheat straw, 2018										
Parameter	Unit	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Moisture	% a.r.	5.80	8.20	8.10	9.60	9.70	9.10	7.70	10.00	8.70
Ash	% d.b.	11.10	10.9	10.7	5.80	6.00	6.50	6.70	6.40	6.60
C	% d.b.	42.20	42.3	42.5	45.29	45.23	44.69	44.51	43.98	44.91
H	% d.b.	5.70	5.70	5.70	5.90	6.00	5.90	6.00	6.00	6.00
N	% d.b.	0.46	0.56	0.53	0.47	0.30	0.33	0.78	0.47	0.61
S	% d.b.	0.10	0.14	0.14	0.08	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.14
Cl	% d.b.	0.77	0.68	1.02	0.52	0.27	0.27	0.44	0.60	0.64
O	% d.b.	39.70	39.7	39.4	42.00	42.10	42.20	41.50	42.50	41.00
Traceability assessment for the maize stalk, 2018										
Parameter	Unit	A	B							
Moisture	% a.r.	6.70	14.70							
Ash	% d.b.	10.60	9.00							
C	% d.b.	42.80	43.70							
H	% d.b.	5.60	5.50							
N	% d.b.	0.80	0.90							
S	% d.b.	0.12	0.10							
Cl	% d.b.	0.75	0.57							
O	% d.b.	39.33	40.23							

4.2.2 Harvesting and Supply Chain

A study was carried out to assess the optimal distance in which the harvesting operation with the current machinery used by the agro-industry (self-loading harvesting operations) is more profitable versus the harvesting with a baling system (normally carried out by suppliers, since APS does not have such machinery).

During each trial, two harvesting systems were tested and compared, the baling and the self-loading wagon systems. The machines used during the tests are common tractors and equipment used by APS suppliers to harvest Lucerne.

Simultaneously, a different study was performed aiming to rank the best suppliers to produce energy and animal feed product. Different criteria were identified for each sector and it was evaluated based on the weight assigned by nine different experts to each criteria according to their experience:

- Energy sector: price, supply stability, moisture, delivery time, distance, ash and chlorine content
- Animal feed sector: protein and ash content, moisture, colour of the material, price, format of supply, social aspects, delivery time and supply stability.

The results were assessed through Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). Afterwards, all the suppliers were evaluated and a score was assigned to each criteria according to the previous experience of the agro-industry with this supplier, this analysis was developed to assess the quality of the material and other aspects. Hence, a simulation model was done with all this input in order to rank the supplier for energy and animal feed uses.

As a result of the first study carried out, regarding wheat straw, distances up to 11.4 km are more profitable to be harvested in bales. In the case of maize stalk it was up to 16.0 km, this higher distance was due to the higher bulk density of loose maize stalks compared to straw (89.3 kg/m³ and 18.6 kg/m³, respectively), which has a significant influence on the results achieved for straw and corn stalk.

Figure 4: Scheme of the harvesting systems compared during the tests

Regarding the second study, the criteria to be considered for each market) were assessed and the weighting factor of each one assigned. In both sectors, the purchasing price and the quality criteria were the most important. Even though, the quality criteria considered were different for each sector, in the case of the energy sector it was based on the moisture content and the ash and chlorine content. In the case of the animal feed it was based on the moisture content, the ash and protein content and the colour of the material. The other criteria in both markets were not as important as the previously mentioned.

4.2.3 Production of the different blends and Product Quality

The whole pelletising line of APS was subject of study as it is the potential part of the facility to be used for the production of biocommodities based on biomass feedstock. A total of 66 tests were performed. Also, the dehydrated line was monitored since it is used to dry the wood in the rotary dryer and an independent tub grinder which it is used as pre-milling process to reduce the size of the wood.

In each test the following information was studied:

- Production and losses obtained in all main equipment of the pelletization line, but also in the dryer and in the tub grinder with each blend.
- Electric and thermal consumption of the previous lines mentioned with each blend.
- Electric consumption exceeding the electric power contracted in all the tests carried out.
- Die used in each test.
- Degree of use of consumables with each test carried out

It was confirmed that products targeting different sectors can be manufactured in the same agro-industry without risky problems of contamination, even though the first hours after changing from one product to another some preventive measures should be taken in order to avoid problems with the quality of the final product

Different wheat straw/maize stalk blends were tested in APS's demo, varying the herbaceous content between 10-100 wt.% for both agrobiomasses. However, the final blends that showed the best economical/quality ratio were:

- Pellets 100 % wheat straw: it could be competitive with agro-biomass with lower quality and prices, as for instance almond shells, olive pits, grape marc, etc.
- Pellets 60/40 % wheat/wood and 72/28 % maize/wood.

However, blend 60/40 wheat/wood was finally selected as the optimal for further analysis.

The analysis carried out and the further validation tests concluded that in order to define energy blends by the agro-industries, the standard ISO-17225-6 can be considered as a possible standard for quality criteria, even though it is the real combustion test performed in the facilities the one that will provide the outputs to define and evaluate the behavior of the fuel.

In order to assess the quality of the energy blend produced the following analysis were performed to each blend:

- Proximate analysis (moisture, volatile matter, fixed carbon, ash content).
- Ultimate analysis (percentage of C, H, N, S, Cl and O).
- Bulk density, durability, and fines percentage.
- Heating value.
- Ash analysis.
- Ash fusibility temperatures.

The blends based on wheat straw showed better results so this reinforces the importance of the traceability assessment to select the best raw materials. Also, it was established that a higher content of wood in the blend does not imply a higher quality in the final blend.

4.2.4 Validation activities

A real validation of these blends was performed

during the combustion tests carried out in CIRCE's laboratories (fixed bed reactor and industrial-scale boiler based on a grill burner). Deposition probes, bottom ash composition and behaviour were evaluated associated to the combustion tests performed, together with SEM and XRD analysis of the bottom and flying ashes generated) and the validation activities that took place at the facilities of different end users (industrial stakeholders).

These tests were quite satisfactory and proved that the blends developed offer good results with the right operational parameters, especially with the blends based on wheat straw, even though in other areas, for instance in which the corn stalk would present difference regarding the composition, this fact can change and the pellets based on corn stalk might achieve better results than the straw blend pellet. This points out the importance to perform a traceability assessment of the raw material used to produce the blend.

The results of the validation of these products is a quite important fact for a potential commercialization of these biofuels, taking into account that herbaceous materials are not very well seen in the energy sector.

Figure 5: Scheme of the experimental test facility.

4.2.5 Necessary investment in the new business line

The following parameters were studied: (i) production and yield for each blend; (ii) Energy consumption (electrical and thermal) for each blend, taking into account the variable cost and the exceed cost; (iii) Raw material cost; (iv) Personnel cost; (v) Losses in the process; (vi) Fixed costs, and (vii) Selling price for the agro-industry and assess if a retailer is necessary considering the commercialization strategy designed for the product.

Figure 6: Cost distribution of the final energy blend selected

As a result, this analysis concluded that the IBLC model is economically profitable (the payback period is less than one year) in the case of APS and probably in agro-industries of the fodder sector with similar conditions accounting with a pelletization line already. However, there are two main risks that should be taken into account in order to fulfil this goal:

- Securing the selling of a new product in the energy market at the targeted price (lower than 150-160 €/t) could be challenging depending on the market conditions, mainly in the first years, since the agro-industry needs to identify attract and retain its clients.
- Raw material cost (average value 40-50 €/t) could increase depending on the year, which could compromise the project economic feasibility (the increase of the raw material to values higher than 50 €/t will for instance strongly affect the selling price of the pellet produced, as it is the main parameter that affects to the final price).

4.3 Demo case in the Grain sector (Sweden)

The following results are part of public deliverable D5.7 'Success case of the integration of a logistics centre into an agro-industry of the grain-milling and feed sector' [8].

Agriculture will play an important role in transition to a sustainable, fossil-free society. In this context, straw has been identified as the agricultural residue with most potential. Straw-based ethanol can further improve utilisation of cereal crops to produce ethanol, as an alternative to fossil-based fuels. The profitability can be further improved by producing biooil from the lignin fraction that remains after ethanol production from straw.

This briefing describes the Swedish demo case designed to supply the Lantmännen ethanol plant in Norrköping with 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw yearly.

4.3.1 Raw material availability

Based on statistics, the potential quantity of straw in Sweden as a whole and in all its 21 counties was compiled. In the whole of Sweden, approximately 1,255,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw are available on-field annually. Of this total potential, about two-thirds (836,000 tonnes) are estimated to remain after deduction of the amount used as feed and bedding in animal production.

Large parts of Sweden's productive area have a humus content exceeding the level (3.4% soil organic matter or 2% C) seen in Sweden as a breakpoint, above which an increase in organic matter can no longer be expected to increase yield. For the Swedish demo case, the sustainability in removing straw from the case study

area of Norrköping and surrounding counties was evaluated from a soil fertility point of view. The assessment revealed the possibility to remove 230,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw from the areas Östergötland, Örebro and Södermanland without reaching the humus limit. The area surrounding Vadstena municipality could provide nearly 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw.

4.3.2 Supply chain

The economic viability of straw-based biorefinery plants depends heavily on the cost of the straw feedstock, with variations in the cost having a large impact on the profitability of the investment. Interviews with farmers and contractors were performed to capture their practical experiences of handling straw.

According to the interviews with farmers, their incentive to harvest straw is dependent on timeliness effects and the risk of delayed establishment of the following crop if the straw is being collected, effects on soil fertility and the price paid for straw. Many farmers saw straw harvesting as a possibility to increase their profits. Contracts over several years were preferred, both by the contractors involved in baling/transport and by the end user of the straw. Farmers should not contract to supply too large a proportion of their straw, as this increases the risk to the farmer and to the end user.

Based on the discussions with farmers and contractors, two different alternatives for the degree of involvement of farmers are in the straw supply system and the connection point between Lantmännen and the farmer were identified.

Two field trials were conducted in Sweden to evaluate whether incorporation of the chaff fraction in the straw swath during combine harvesting of winter wheat can increase the total amount of harvested residues. The results showed a small increase in baled biomass with chaff incorporation. However, the results from the two years were inconsistent, indicating a need for further studies. A field test was conducted to evaluate anaerobic storage of moist straw bales wrapped in plastic. This proved to be an efficient storage method, but the additional costs of plastic wrap, labour and machinery amounted to around €30 per tonne of straw.

Figure 7: Schematic diagram showing two alternatives (Alt.) in the contact and responsibilities between farmers and Lantmännen

4.3.3 Biofuel production

Pretreatment of lignocellulosic material is often required to make the cellulose and hemicellulose more accessible to enzymatic hydrolysis to monomeric sugars. Two promising methods, hot water pretreatment and organosolv, were tested in addition to steam explosion, to produce material suitable for hydrolysis and fermentation. These gave two main feedstock streams:

carbohydrates for fermentation and a lignin slurry for the hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) process. All methods yielded material for further studies. After pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis of the fractionated material was employed to split cellulose (and hemicellulose) into mono-sugars. Hydrolysis worked well for all pretreated materials.

Figure 8: Continuous rig for hydrothermal liquefaction.

Fermentation worked well for material from hot water pretreatment if using detoxification, but could not be performed on material from the organosolv pretreatment. For the straw pretreated with hot water, fermentation resulted in an ethanol titre of 47 g/L and yield above 0.45 g ethanol/g glucose and xylose consumed. Further development work is needed to achieve useful fermentation of the organosolv fractions.

The carbon-rich lignin residue from hydrolysis of wheat straw was investigated as a feedstock for the HTL process. A continuous rig was designed, constructed and commissioned during the project period. Based on results from initial studies, the following conditions were used when running the HTL pilot rig: 340 °C, 15 minutes retention time, 200 bar pressure and 10% lignin slurry containing 10% additive. Biooils were successfully produced from hydrolysis lignin from wheat straw, with the oil yield varying between 36-96 % including additive and the char yield lying below 22 %. The oil quality (as HHV) for the different samples varied between 30 and 37 MJ/kg. Vegetable oils showed promise as carriers and use of alkali hydroxide as catalyst reduced the amount of biochar produced. In addition to biooil, biochar is also produced in the HTL process but, since it can be considered a low-value biochar due to its high ash content, the interest in the project was in minimising biochar yield.

4.3.4 Product quality

The heating value of the biooils produced (around 35 MJ/kg) was lower than for crude fossil oil (range 42-47 MJ/kg), but in line with that reported for biooils derived from other lignocellulosic feedstocks. The viscosity of the biooils produced varied significantly, from 56 to 11 306 mPa·s. The biochar contained a high proportion of ash (61.5% DS, mostly silica) and a relatively low content of carbon (27.6% DS). This means that the possible market application considered, as energy pellets, is not relevant.

4.3.5 Market analysis

The properties of straw-based bioethanol do not differ from those of conventional bioethanol. This means

that the market for the product is already known to Lantmännen. There are many possible applications for HTL-produced biooil. Analysis of the biooils obtained during the project showed that, so far, none is ready for transportation applications. This means that these biooils need to be upgraded prior to application. Two interesting applications for further studies, considering market potential and technical challenges, are as a marine fuel after light upgrading and as an additive to asphalt. Biochar pellets are reasonably easy to produce and test for calorific content and usability. However, the HTL-biochar produced is not suitable for utilisation as energy pellets due to the high ash content. The properties of HTL biochar also do not meet the requirements for addition to concrete or customer requirements for soil improvement applications.

4.3.6 Cost structure and business model

Integration of a fermentation step to produce 2nd-generation bioethanol with the HTL process to produce biooil is a good way to maximise use of the raw material, in this case the straw provided by the Integrated Biomass Logistic Centre (IBLC). In the final business model, wastewater treatment to produce biogas was added to convert residual components of the raw material into high-value products.

Figure 9: The assumed business case process layout, including 2nd-generation bioethanol production, biooil production and anaerobic wastewater treatment producing biogas.

\The current business model gives a net profit, but the

profit is not high enough for the business model to be economically feasible. The major challenges are the high price of straw and of enzyme for enzymatic hydrolysis and the small HTL unit, resulting in high operating costs. Reduced straw price (by 30%) significantly improved the scenario, but was still not sufficient. Introduction of an additional raw material would enable scaling up of the HTL unit, which would improve the business case. This raw material could be in the form of pure lignin or other types of waste/secondary biomass with high lignin content. It could be supplied either directly into the HTL process, especially as pure lignin, or added to the bioethanol process as a pretreatment step. The business models developed in this project have taken many steps towards economic feasibility, which is now within reach after some adjustments. In addition, the new IBLC – biofuels from straw – gives new opportunities for several stakeholders for a fossil-free society.

4.4 Replication potential of IBLC model in other agroindustries

The following results are included in public deliverable D7.3 ‘Executive report from the active multi-actor participation including show cases. Replication Potential’ [9]

The main objective of this task was to transfer the most important result of the project to other regions in selected sectors with a high potential for replicability of IBLC concept, therefore allowing to put in real context the results and conclusions achieved during the project.

According to results reported in public deliverable D6.2 ‘Basic analysis of targeted agricultural sectors’ [10], the vegetable oils sector was excluded because it had low potential and no interest was detected in any of the partners countries. For the sugar sector, despite low potential and interest in most countries assessed, in Sweden a large sugar company did show interest and a reasonable potential to implement the IBLC concept therefore, it was decided to still consider the sector and to give it a different approach.

Thus, the sectors studied in this case were: wine, feed and fodder, olive oil, grain and sugar sectors. As explained in the methodology above, the first step that was taken after the determination of countries and sectors involved, was the identification of regions with high potential for IBLC development.

Finally, the planned distribution in relation to the countries, sectors and regions involved in this phase was as shown in the table below:

Table II: Distribution on countries, sectors and regions

Distribution on countries, sectors and regions					
Country/sector Region	Wine	Feed & Fodder	Olive oil	Grain	Sugar
Sweden				Skåne County	X
Greece			Crete (Chania)		
Spain	Castilla – La Mancha	Aragón	Castilla – La Mancha		X
Ukraine				Poltava	
Serbia	Šumadija-Great Morava region (Lapovo) and West Morava region (Aleksandrovac)				

As a result of these activities, the following summary of replicability factors was extracted.

In terms of regulations, all the sectors were aligned with the IBLC model (wine, feed and fodder, olive oil,

grain and sugar). The reform of the CAP will increasingly be linked to environmental issues and the use of agricultural residues will be imposed. In this context, the transition period must be accompanied by incentives rather than penalties. Thus, the current and especially future production paradigm will be based on the circular economy and the efficiency in the use of resources.

As for the market and new products, however, some discrepancies were found between the sectors. Even it was found that in all the studied sectors the implementation of IBLC might be viable and could represent an opportunity for diversification the business line and valorization of different residues/by-products (especially in the market of biomaterials and biochemicals), only the case of the sugar sector showed a solid interest of the agents in being active in the search for other more complex products from agricultural biomass and the residues obtained from its regular production process.

Regarding the awareness of the sectors, all of them identified this initiatives as interested by the society, as they would improve the environmental performance of the activity, create jobs and, in principle, generate value from a material for which until then there was no other use than combustion without energy recovery, encouraging thus the IBLC concept.

All sectors found the implementation of IBLC model as economically interesting, considering these initiatives as a great opportunity for the rural world and with a great potential for the use of by-products from the agro-food industry, as long as the secondary activity would increase the profitability and income of the agroindustry.

Each sector agreed showed a great interest of collaboration and willingness to implement the IBLC concept, the cooperatives being identified as a very potential actor to become IBLCs. It was also found that society and public policies, so as local councils who play a key and influencing role in the path towards circular economy models, are willing to promote this model.

As for the technological aspects, wine and olive oil sectors were the ones which showed higher replicability, since there has been a notable increase in the recent years of biomass boilers installation in these sectors.

Finally, also all sectors were aligned when thinking about synergies with other flows of biobased feedstocks which should ensure that the IBLC processes larger volumes and scales up, as well as reduce the risk of feedstock shortages due to climate reasons, for example.

5 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 IBLC demo case in the Olive oil sector (Greece)

In the scope of the olive oil sector, the majority of activities in the AGROinLOG project, have been focused on the exploitation of olive tree prunings as a main activity of an IBLC. During the project, activities have been performed to demonstrate / validate / prove the technical feasibility of each value chain step, thus evaluating the potential pathways of NUTRIA towards its conversion into an IBLC. Different new products are obtained with different market potential: i) OTP hog fuel, ii) OTP pellet, iii) electricity.

Even though OTP pellets could compete with well-established industrial fuels, in terms of combustion efficiency and emissions, their cost is considerably

higher, making them an unattractive solution for substituting industrial fuels. As a result, the concept where NUTRIA invests on a pellet line is slightly risky as their absorbance in the market is still questionable. On the contrary, the use of OTP in the form of hog fuel seems to be a promising solution. It is a more competitive biofuel due to its reduced fuel cost. However, it faces several challenges as well, as its need of a suitable feeding system to burn such fuel. Furthermore, OTP hog fuel has significantly lower (energy) density compared to pellets, thus increasing the transportation costs. In this light, its targeted end users should be in close range from the IBLC. Finally, the concept of power plant could be the most rational one when mobilizing high quantities of raw material, as the whole amount of harvested OTP would be consumed to generate power, thus securing the demand of the harvested OTP. In addition, with a guaranteed reference tariff for 20 years, the investment of NUTRIA in such IBLC concept, seems to be the most profitable.

5.2 IBLC demo case in the Feed and fodder sector (Spain)

It has been demonstrated that the integration of a Biomass Logistics Centre based on the production of blend pellets inside the fodder sector is possible and profitable with a low initial investment for the agro-industries, since they already account with the majority of equipment necessary for carrying out the new activity.

Therefore, it can be a business line to be considered by the agro-industries during the period of lower activity which takes place usually from December to March, in order to avoid seasonality and to create full time work. The results highlight that one of the main advantages of the IBLC model is its flexibility to adapt their secondary business line to the market conditions in order to optimize the profitability of the agro-industry while contributing to diversify the business.

The main risk associated to the profitability of this alternative business line, is securing the commercialization of the product, since normally agro-industries do not account with a broad knowledge of the energy market. For this reason, it could be interesting to consider the option of establishing relationships with other intermediates (as energy services companies, biomass suppliers, ...) to facilitate the penetration of the new product in the market.

Finally, regarding the other applications studied for pure herbaceous pellets (biocomposites boards, thermoplastic reinforced with natural fibers, adsorbent for hydrocarbons, activated carbon for supercapacitors, furfural and levulinic acid), the results obtained were very promising, although in the short-term the commercialization of this products is difficult since the market is not yet well developed.

5.3 IBLC demo case in the Grain sector (Sweden)

Regarding straw potential and capacity to harvest and handle straw, it is possible to supply the Swedish demonstration case in Norrköping with 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw. In the surrounding regions, as much as 230,000 tonnes would be available after taking account of any limitations regarding soil fertility aspects and the straw needed for animal production.

Lantmännen has good IBLC preconditions to widen its current business model with production of second-generation ethanol. It has well-established contacts with

farmers and suppliers, a sales organisation for straw and ethanol, etc.

Lantmännen can produce ethanol from straw and has successfully learned to produce biooil with high yield from the lignin fraction remaining after ethanol production. Wastewater from the production can be utilised for biogas production. Thus, the profitability of the business model is based on three products (ethanol, biooil and biogas), thereby spreading the risks.

There are a wide range of possible markets and applications for the biooil. For most applications, however, the biooil needs to be upgraded to some extent, which significantly increases the investment costs. No market for the biochar produced in the project has been identified, mainly due to the high ash content.

The current business model for the demonstration case is estimated to give a net profit, although not enough to be economically viable. The major challenges are the high cost of straw, enzymes for hydrolysis and operation of the biooil unit. Scaling up the biooil unit and possibly also introducing an additional raw material source might help to improve the economic viability of the business model.

5.4 Replication potential of IBLC model in other agroindustries

According to the previously detailed results, it can be concluded that a great potential of replication was determined in all the studied sectors. The different sectors analyzed (wine, feed and fodder, olive oil, grain and sugar) were well aligned with the IBLC model in terms of regulations. Each of them showed a great interest in of collaboration and found the implementation of this model as a great opportunity in economic terms, for the diversification of their business lines, so as to promote the rural development.

From the technological point of view, the wine and olive oil sectors were the ones with higher replicability due to the significant increase of biomass boilers installation in these sectors.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] inr.gr. (2014). " Economic Data for industries in the olive sector." from <http://www.inr.gr/?p=a2097>.
- [2] Michailides, M., P. Panagopoulos, C. S. Akratos, A. G. Tekerlekopoulou and D. V. Vayenas (2011). "A full-scale system for aerobic biological treatment of olive mill wastewater." *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology* 86(6): 888-892
- [3] Deliverable D4.8 'Success case of the integration of a logistics centre into an agro-industry of the olive oil sector' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961
- [4] M.A. Kougioumtzis, E. Karampinis, P. Grammelis, E. Kakaras, Exploitation of Olive Tree Prunings. Evaluation of an Integrated Harvesting Demonstration in Central Greece, 27th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, 2019
- [5] Suardi, A.; Latterini, F.; Alfano, V.; Palmieri, N.; Bergonzoli, S.; Karampinis, E.; Kougioumtzis, M.A.; Grammelis, P.; Pari, L. Machine Performance and Hog Fuel Quality Evaluation in Olive Tree Pruning Harvesting Conducted Using a Towed Shredder on Flat and Hilly Fields. *Energies* 2020, 13, 1713.
- [6] Frost and Sullivan, from <https://store.frost.com/the-european-polyphenols-market.html>.
- [7] Deliverable D3.7 'Success case of an IBLC into an agroindustry of the animal feed sector' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961
- [8] Deliverable D5.7 'Success case of the integration of a logistics centre into an agro-industry of the grain-milling and feed sector' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961
- [9] Deliverable D7.3 'Executive report from the active multi-actor participation including show cases. Replication Potential' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961
- [10] Deliverable D6.2 'Basic analysis of targeted agricultural sectors' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961
- [11] Deliverable, D6.1 'Updated conceptual description of an IBLC' AGROinLOG project, Grant Agreement N°727961

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8 LOGO SPACE

